

USE OF PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS IN REGRESSION PROBLEM

¹Sujata Suvarnapathaki

¹Associate Professor

¹Department of Statistics,

¹Ramnarain Ruia Autonomous College, Mumbai, India

Abstract: The problem of multicollinearity arises in a regression model when the independent variables are highly correlated to each other. Multicollinearity does not limit the possibility of obtaining a good model or affect inferences about expected responses. However, it has two serious consequences viz. a) The model parameters are highly unstable since the standard errors of their estimates are inflated b) The model fails to predict for out-of-sample data accurately. It is important to check for multicollinearity in regression analysis.

Two basic indicators of multicollinearity are a) High Pairwise Correlation among the independent variables and b) Significant “F Value” for the hypothesis for the global testing which indicates that at least one of the explanatory variables is significantly influencing the dependent variable but there are very few significant t Values for individual testing. The most widely used method for the detection of multicollinearity is “Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)”. The basic assumption in Regression analysis is independent variables among themselves should be weakly correlated i.e., absence of multicollinearity. Hence, the problem of multicollinearity can be resolved by different approaches viz. i) Drop one of the independent variables, which is explained by others ii) Use Principal Component Regression.

This paper discusses the application of Principal Component Analysis in the Regression Problem to address the issue of multicollinearity.

Index Terms - Regression analysis, Multicollinearity, VIF, Principal Component Analysis, Principal Component Regression

I. INTRODUCTION

The Multiple Linear Regression technique is a predictive Modelling technique that includes one numeric dependent variable and several explanatory variables. Using the historical data, a mathematical equation is built that is used for predicting the outcome. The mathematical model for Multiple linear regression is given by,

$$Y = b_0 + b_1X_1 + X_2 + \dots + X_p + e$$

Where, Y is a dependent variable and X_1, X_2, \dots, X_p are independent variables.

$b_0, b_1, b_2, \dots, b_p$ are the parameters of the Model and ‘e’ is the Random Error Component.

The method of Least Squares is used to estimate the model parameters.

Multicollinearity is defined as a problem in predictive modeling if there is a strong linear relationship among the independent variables. Multicollinearity has some serious consequences. 1) Parameters of the model are highly unstable as the standard errors of their estimates are inflated. 2) The model may look perfect for a given sample. Although, it fails to predict accurately for out-of-sample data.

Indications of the Problem:

There are some indicators of the presence of multicollinearity.

- 1) High pairwise correlations among independent variables. (Sufficient but not necessary)
- 2) Significant F value (based on ANOVA) but very few significant t values.
- 3) One of the eigenvalues of the correlation matrix of independent variables is close to zero.

Frequently, Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is used to detect the presence of multicollinearity. VIF is calculated for each independent variable.

$$VIF = \frac{1}{Tolerance}$$

$$Tolerance = 1 - R^2$$

Where, R^2 , is the coefficient of determination obtained by building a Regression Model using each independent variable as a dependent variable and the rest as the independent variables. Each R^2 measures how much variation in the independent variables is being explained by the other independent variables. If the value of R^2 is high then there is a problem of multicollinearity.

The problem is severe if any of the above R^2 is greater than or equal to 0.80 or $VIF > 5$.

If multicollinearity is detected, then the remedial measures can be taken based on the situation viz. a) Drop one of the independent variables which is explained by others b) Use Principal Component Regression.

II. METHODOLOGY:

This paper aims to address the issue of multicollinearity in Multiple Linear Regression and compares Principal Component Regression to overcome the problem of multicollinearity. The above methods are compared using four open datasets Viz. California Housing Data, Diabetes Data, Hitters Data and Concrete Compressive Strength Data.

Multiple Linear Regression model is built for each dataset mentioned above after partitioning each data in Training data and Test Data. VIFs are observed to be high and hence a remedial measure is applied.

a) Multiple Linear Regression:

Multiple linear regression technique is used as a predictive modelling method in a situation where one continuous dependent variable say, Y may be influenced by more than one independent variable viz. X_1, X_2, \dots, X_p . The mathematical model for Multiple linear regression is given by,

$$Y = b_0 + b_1X_1 + X_2 + \dots + X_p + e$$

Where, Y is a dependent variable and X_1, X_2, \dots, X_p are independent Variables. $b_0, b_1, b_2, \dots, b_p$ are the parameters of the Model and 'e' is the Random Error Component.

The parameters of the model are estimated by the Least Square Method which includes minimizing the error sum of squares.

The goodness of the Model is determined by the Coefficient of determination, R^2 .

R^2 is the proportion of variation in the dependent variable, explained by the independent variables.

$$R^2 = \frac{\text{Explained Variation}}{\text{Total Variation}} \quad R^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{Y}_i - \bar{Y})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \bar{Y})^2} \quad 0 \leq R^2 \leq 1$$

Although, R^2 is good and other results are promising it is important to validate the assumptions of the model. One of the most important assumptions of Multiple Linear Regression is that the independent variables among themselves are weakly correlated. (Absence of multicollinearity).

Variance Inflation Factor, $VIF > 5$ indicates the problem of multicollinearity.

A variable with $VIF > 5$, is explained by other independent variables. Since the presence of multicollinearity has serious consequences, it is necessary to use a remedial measure to resolve the issue and predict the value of dependent variables with greater accuracy.

If one of the explanatory variables has a problem then it may be dropped from the analysis but in case there are many variables with $VIF > 5$, techniques like Principal Component Regression may be used to resolve multicollinearity issue.

b) Principal Component Analysis (PCA):

PCA is the most widely used multivariate method.

PCA uses the correlation structure of original variables and derives p linear combinations which are uncorrelated. Each PC provides unique information about the data. Although 'p' principal components are derived, the first 'k' principal components are expected to explain most of the variability in the data.

From p original variables: X_1, X_2, \dots, X_p derive p new variables Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_p

$$Y_1 = a_{11} X_1 + a_{12} X_2 + a_{13} X_3 + \dots + a_{1p} X_p$$

$$Y_2 = a_{21} X_1 + a_{22} X_2 + a_{23} X_3 + \dots + a_{2p} X_p$$

$$Y_3 = a_{31} X_1 + a_{32} X_2 + a_{33} X_3 + \dots + a_{3p} X_p$$

$$Y_p = a_{p1} X_1 + a_{p2} X_2 + a_{p3} X_3 + \dots + a_{pp} X_p$$

such that Y_k 's are uncorrelated (orthogonal).

Variance-Covariance matrix can be used if variables are measured on the same units. Although, Correlation matrix is a better choice for PCA than the variance-covariance matrix. The variance-covariance matrix of the standardized variables is same as the correlation matrix of the original variables.

First Principal Component: A linear combination $a'_1 X$, which maximizes $V(a'X)$ subject to $a'a = 1$

Second Principal Component: A linear combination $a'_2 X$ which maximizes $V(a'X)$ subject to $a'a = 1$ and $CoV(a'_2 X, a'_1 X) = 0$

Third Principal Component: A linear combination $a'_3 X$ which maximizes $V(a'X)$ subject to $a'a = 1$ and $CoV(a'_3 X, a'_2 X) = 0$ and so on.

Obtain correlation matrix R of 'p' analysis variables

Let $(\lambda_1, e_1), (\lambda_2, e_2), \dots, (\lambda_p, e_p)$ be the eigenvalue-eigenvector pairs where, $(\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_p \geq 0)$

The i^{th} Principal Component is given by

$$Y_i = a_i' X$$

$$Y_i = a_{1i} X_1 + a_{2i} X_2 + \dots + a_{pi} X_p \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, p$$

where

$$V(Y_i) = \lambda_i \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, p$$

$$CoV(Y_i, Y_k) = 0 \quad i \neq k$$

If A the $(k \times k)$ matrix and I be the $k \times k$ identity matrix. Then the scalars satisfying the polynomial equation $|A - \lambda I| = 0$ are called the Eigenvalues (characteristic roots) of matrix A. Eigenvectors are obtained by solving $AX = \lambda X$. 'p' principal components are derived but data reduction is achieved with first 'k' PC's. One can retain principal components associated with eigenvalue more than '1'.

The variance of principal component is equal to associated eigenvalue. This is known as "Kaiser Criterion". Another method to determine the correct number of PCs to use is to look at a scree plot and check for "elbow".

Principal Component Analysis is not inherently used for regression tasks.

c) Principal Component Regression(PCR):

PCR is a regression technique that combines elements of both PCA and linear regression.

In PCR, PCA is first performed on the predictor variables to obtain a reduced set of principal components. These principal components are then used as predictors in a linear regression model to predict the response variable.

In the Principal Component Regression, the first k principal components are used as the independent variables instead of the original X(explanatory) variables. Each PC is a linear combination of all X variables. The final model is expressed in terms of original independent variables for ease of interpretation using back transformation.

In the first step, the original **p** variables are transformed into a new set of orthogonal or uncorrelated variables called "Principal Components".

In the second step, after the elimination of the least important principal components, a multiple regression analysis of the response variable against the reduced set of principal components is performed using the OLS (Ordinary Least Square) estimation. In the third step, the model equation is back transformed in terms of the original variables.

The statistical model for Principal Component Regression (PCR) is as below.

$$Y = a_0 + a_1 PC_1 + a_2 PC_2 + \dots + a_k PC_k + e'$$

Principal Components are obtained using R. The function, **princomp()** from base R performs PCA on the given numeric data matrix. **formula**= contains the numeric variables. **~.** ensures all variables are taken. **cor=T** indicates that calculations should be done using the Correlation Matrix. **summary()** generates the summary of PCA.

Using R, **pcr()** in package **pls** performs Principal Component Regression. **ncomp** is the number of components to be included in the model. **scale=TRUE** indicates X is scaled by dividing each variable by its standard deviation. This ensures data is standardized before running the PCR algorithm.

The summary gives the proportion of variation explained by each principal component and also the cumulative proportion of variation. The number of principal components that explain approximately 80% proportion of variation cumulatively can be used for principal component regression.

In this research paper, four open datasets with the issue of multicollinearity, are analyzed using Multiple Linear Regression and Principal Component Regression.

The Root Mean Square Error(RMSE) is calculated for the "Test Data" of each dataset used for the Multiple Linear Regression and Principal Component Regression.

$$RMSE = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}}{n}$$

Where, n = Number of observations, y_i is the observed value of Y and \hat{y}_i is the predicted value of Y using the Regression Model. RMSE is used for assessing the performance of regression models. A lower RMSE value indicates that the model's predictions are closer to the actual data, signifying better alignment between the predicted and observed values. On the other hand, a higher RMSE value suggests that the model's predictions exhibit a larger average deviation from the actual data, indicating lower accuracy in its predictions.

Dataset 1: California Housing Data (Source: Pace, R. Kelley, and Ronald Barry. "Sparse spatial autoregressions." Statistics & Probability Letters 33.3 (1997): 291-297, Kaggle.com)

Table 1: Partial Data (California Housing Data)

Longitude	Latitude	Housing_Median_Age	Total_Rooms	Total_Bedrooms	Population	Households	Median_Income	Median_House_Value
-122.23	37.88	41	880	129	322	126	8.3252	452600
-122.22	37.86	21	7099	1106	2401	1138	8.3014	358500
-122.24	37.85	52	1467	190	496	177	7.2574	352100
-122.25	37.85	52	1274	235	558	219	5.6431	341300
-122.25	37.85	52	1627	280	565	259	3.8462	342200
-122.25	37.85	52	919	213	413	193	4.0368	269700

1. Longitude: A Measure Of How Far West A House Is; A Higher Value Is Farther West,
 2. Latitude: A Measure Of How Far North A House Is; A Higher Value Is Farther North,
 3. Housing_Median_Age: Median Age Of A House Within A Block; A Lower Number Is A Newer Building
 4. Total_Rooms: Total Number Of Rooms Within A Block
 5. Total_Bedrooms: Total Number Of Bedrooms Within A Block
 6. Population: Total Number Of People Residing Within A Block
 7. Households: Total Number Of Households, A Group Of People Residing Within A Home Unit, For A Block
 8. Median_Income: Median Income For Households Within A Block Of Houses (Measured In Tens Of Thousands Of Us Dollars)
 9. Median_House_Value: Median House Value for Households Within A Block (Measured In Us Dollars)
- Median_House_Value is a dependent variable.

Dataset 2: Diabetes Data (Source: Kaggle.com)

Table 2: Partial Data (Diabetes Data)

AGE	SEX	BMI	BP	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	Y
59	2	32.1	101	157	93.2	38	4	4.8598	87	151
48	1	21.6	87	183	103.2	70	3	3.8918	69	75
72	2	30.5	93	156	93.6	41	4	4.6728	85	141
24	1	25.3	84	198	131.4	40	5	4.8903	89	206

- AGE: Age in years, SEX: Gender, BMI: Body Mass Index, BP: Average Blood Pressure,
 S1: TC, T-Cells (A Type of White Blood Cells),
 S2: LDL, Low-Density Lipoproteins, S3: HDL, High-Density Lipoproteins
 S4: TSH, Thyroid Stimulating Hormone
 S5: LTG, Lamotrigine
 S6: GLU, Blood Sugar Level
 Y: Measure of Disease Progression One Year After Baseline

Dataset 3: Hitters Data (Source: Kaggle.com)

Table 3: Partial Data (Hitters Data)

AtBat	Hits	HmRun	Runs	RBI	Walks	Years	CAtBat	CHits	CHmRun	CRuns	CRBI	CWalks	PutOuts	Assists	Errors	Salary
293	66	1	30	29	14	1	293	66	1	30	29	14	446	33	20	--
315	81	7	24	38	39	14	3449	835	69	321	414	375	632	43	10	475
479	130	18	66	72	76	3	1624	457	63	224	266	263	880	82	14	480
496	141	20	65	78	37	11	5628	1575	225	828	838	354	200	11	3	500
321	87	10	39	42	30	2	396	101	12	48	46	33	805	40	4	91.5
594	169	4	74	51	35	11	4408	1133	19	501	336	194	282	421	25	750

A data frame with 322 observations of major league players on the following 16 variables Viz. AtBat: Number of times at bat in 1986, Hits: Number of hits in 1986, HmRun: Number of home runs in 1986, Runs: Number of runs in 1986, RBI: Number of runs batted in in 1986, Walks: Number of walks in 1986, Years: Number of years in the major leagues, CAtBat: Number of times at bat during his career, CHits: Number of hits during his career, CHmRun: Number of home runs during his career, CRuns: Number of runs during his career. CRBI: Number of runs batted in during his career, CWalks: Number of walks during his career, PutOuts: Number of put outs in 1986, Assists: Number of assists in 1986, Errors: Number of errors in 1986, Salary: 1987 annual salary on opening day in thousands of dollars(Dependent Variable)

Dataset 4: Concrete Compressive Strength Data (Source: UCI Machine Learning Repository)

Table 4: Partial Data (Concrete Compressive Strength Data)

Sr. No.	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	Age	Strength
1	540	0	0	162	2.5	1040	676	28	79.99
2	540	0	0	162	2.5	1055	676	28	61.89
3	332.5	142.5	0	228	0	932	594	270	40.27
4	332.5	142.5	0	228	0	932	594	365	41.05
5	198.6	132.4	0	192	0	978.4	825.5	360	44.3
6	266	114	0	228	0	932	670	90	47.03

The dataset has 1030 observations and has one dependent variable and 8 independent variables. The variables are Cement (component 1) kg in a m3 mixture, Blast Furnace Slag (component 2), Fly Ash (component 3), Water (component 4), Superplasticizer (component 5), Coarse Aggregate (component 6), Fine Aggregate (component 7), Age-Day (1~365) and Concrete compressive strength (Dependent variable).

In this study, each dataset mentioned above is divided into two subsets: "Training Data," which comprises 70% of the original data, and "Test Data," which includes the remaining 30% of the original data. Multiple linear regression is applied to the Training Data of each dataset. The analysis has revealed that the Variance Inflation Factors (VIFs) for the independent variables are high in all four datasets. Consequently, Principal Component regression is applied on both the Training and Test datasets. To evaluate the model performance, the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) is computed for the Test Data in each dataset.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Using the R programming language, a Multiple Linear Regression Model is constructed for each dataset. The summary of VIFs for the independent variables in these four datasets is presented below.

Table 5: Summary of VIFs for Datasets

Sr No.	Dataset	VIFs for the independent variables									
1	California Housing Data		Longitude	Latitude	Housing_Median_Age	Total_Rooms	Total_Bedrooms	Population	Households	Median_Income	
			8.75	8.85	1.27	12.27	35.24	6.22	34.51	1.73	
2	Diabetes Data	AGE	SEX	BMI	BP	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6
		1.22	1.23	1.52	1.44	59.93	39.14	15.64	9.12	9.68	1.57
3	Hitters Data		AtBat	Hits	HmRun	Runs	RBI	Walks	Years	CAtBat	
			25.32	31.57	7.77	15.78	12.5	4.51	9.06	276.65	
			CHits	CHmRun	CRuns	CRBI	CWalks	PutOuts	Assists	Errors	
			587.45	51.74	162.15	160.93	23.19	1.35	2.85	2.37	

4	Concrete Compressive Strength Data			C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	Age
				7.58	7.27	6.32	6.8	2.85	5.16	7.08	1.12

Elevated VIFs signal the presence of multicollinearity, a common issue in the data. To address this problem, Principal Component Regression is employed as a corrective measure. Subsequently, RMSE values are computed for the Test datasets to assess the model's performance.

The summary is as below.

Table No. 6: Summary of Comparison of RMSE for Test Datasets using MLR and PCR

Sr. No.	Dataset Name	Number of independent Variables	Number of Cases	Number of cases in Training Data	Number of cases in Test Data	RMSE for Test data using MLR	RMSE for Test Data using PCR
1	California Housing Data	8	20433	14303	6130	69013.53	425.3849
2	Diabetes Data	10	442	310	132	51.4863	0.4895
3	Hitters Data	16	322	225	97	409.8611	58.4010
4	Concrete Compressive Strength Data	8	1030	721	309	10.5919	0.1322

The results presented above demonstrate that the Principal Component Regression outperforms Multiple Linear Regression when it comes to handling out-of-sample data in presence of Multicollinearity. While a common practice for addressing moderate to severe multicollinearity is to eliminate independent variables, this approach can result in the loss of valuable information. On the other hand, Principal Component Regression proves to be a superior alternative for dealing with multicollinearity issues while preserving the richness of the data.

By reducing the number of predictors using PCA, PCR can help mitigate multicollinearity issues and potentially improve the stability, interpretability and applicability of the regression model.

REFERENCE:

A. Research Papers

- [1] Chigozie Kelechi: Regression and Principal Component Analyses: a Comparison Using Few Regressors, American Journal of Mathematics and Statistics 2(1):1-5
- [2] Jolliffe, I. T. (1982). A note on the use of principal components in regression. Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series C (Applied Statistics), 31(3), 300-303.
- [3] Mevik, B. H., & Wehrens, R. (2007). The pls package: Principal component and partial least squares regression in R. Journal of Statistical Software, 18(2), 1-24.
- [4] Krishnan, S., & Narayan, A. (2018). Comparison of linear regression and principal component regression in quantifying relationship between environmental variables and ground-level ozone concentrations. Journal of Environmental Engineering, 144(7), 04018036.

B. Books

- [1] "Principal Component Analysis" by I. T. Jolliffe